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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“HARDER YOU ARE TO OTHERS, SOFTER YOU ARE TO YOUR DAUGHTER”

The world observes how firm and forceful are thee
A booming voice, piercing through everything.
However, your rough edges untangle when you look at me.
Guarded, and concealed tenderness of a king

They speak about your resilience, your unwavering strength,
The way you persevere in the midst of heat
However, I am aware of the hands that gently hold me.
The parent who eases all suffering the world can give

The braver you are to the outside environment,
When I run to your ground, you get softer undoubtedly
Kind to me, but a stronghold to many—
A love as strong and powerful as the sea

Thus, allow them to imagine whatever they knew
A steel-tempered man, unrestrained and unwell
But whether there is happiness or sorrow, I will always know
My precious life is shielded by your hardest shell.